

Biological Existence from Medicalisation to Biomedicalization

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ABSTRACT

The process of medicalisation began around the end of the 18th century^[1] due to the emergence of the bourgeoisie and its values, which included the right to be healthy and carry out one’s everyday skills, actions which in turn entailed the creation of a state’s wealth. In this period, biopolitics was established, a new form of power administration. This made use of medicine to create behaviour that was useful for social activity, shifting the focus from the administration of the law to bringing subjects back within norms through therapeutic action.^[2] This stemmed from the fact that the key issue in governing a population is to maintain the workforce and to establish, through health, modes of behaviour that are valuable in its preservation. Genetic engineering and new forms of biomedicine have changed the paradigm of medicalisation into biomedicalisation, marking a shift from medical control over external nature to the control and transformation of inner nature. Through this optimisation, man regains a natural mode of expression within social norms.

Keywords: Medicalisation; Biomedicalisation; Biopolitics

Cultural-historical trends have led the union between medicine and state to become the source of current common morality. In particular, the process of medicalization^[3] is not only the effect of a specific type of power but represents a cultural framework that drives actions of power. This process of administering key conduct based on the concepts of normal and abnormal has replaced the concepts of just and unjust, leading subjects to consider themselves wholly within this category and inexorably linking the processes of their subjectification with medical actions aimed at re-establishing a natural concept of health and the creation of a system of moral understanding based entirely on the concept of natural therapeutic gestures.^[4]

It is therefore unthinkable to claim that the process of medicalisation takes place due to the will of the medical profession, state power, or pharmaceutical companies,^[5] but rather that the moral construction that drives human activity nowadays is essentially rooted within the dimension of therapeutic meaning; the three poles of power mentioned above are linked to each other without any possibility of separation.

It could be said that nowadays the medicalisation of life is not merely a phenomenon within the conceptual and moral framework of our age but constitutes its very framework. Proof of this is the fact that citizenship itself, i.e. being an active part of community life,^[6] is conceived in the light of biological values. The term biological

citizenship is used to embrace all the facets of the idea that citizenship is linked to beliefs about the biological existence of human beings as men and women. Today, the state is organised around natural norms that refer to man's own biology, implying that citizens themselves think in terms of health and illness, hence in biological-natural terms.^[7] The enemy of these citizens is the pathological state, the abnormal. The remedy for this enemy is the therapeutic possibilities offered by medicine, so much so that much of the conversation among people focuses on health and has as its subject the natural aspect of human expression. In fact, building biological citizens also entails creating people who have a certain form of relationship with each other. Such citizens use biologically enriched language to describe aspects of themselves or their identities and to give voice to their feelings of unhappiness, ailments or dilemmas. For example, they describe themselves as having a high blood cholesterol level, as vulnerable to stress, as immuno-compromised, and as hereditarily predisposed to schizophrenia or breast cancer.^[8] They use this phraseology, and the forms of calculations associated with it, to make judgements about how they could or should react to the type of things they fear and the kind of life which they can aspire to. In part, of course, the language that shapes self-understanding is disseminated through influential channels:^[9] health education, medical advice, publications by specialists and more. This is instrumental in understanding how the frame of meaning within which the subject makes their assertions is a biological one, where biological is to be understood as a reference to the natural, constituted by health.^[10] Individual subjectivity also constitutes a pole of power in the craving and desire for new drugs and new cures, since individuals conceive of their own lives on precisely this basis.

Today, people tend to observe from a perspective of natural decompensation. All forms of pain experienced are connected with a frame of meaning linked to medicalisation, i.e. that which operates in the sphere of the normal and the pathological. All of this is not, however, demanded solely by the doctor, the state or the pharmaceutical industry's desire to sell medicine but is desired by the subject himself, who is unable to conceive of himself except within his own dimension of meaning dictated by the moral framework^[11] within which he exists, thus framing medicalisation as a phenomenon where it is impossible to identify an individual who holds this mechanism.

Present-day biological citizenship entrusts its hopes to medical science, since each of its projects, both individual and collective, cannot help but be linked to the concept of health, therapy and cures that scientific practice will produce in the future.^[12] The subject's demand is, therefore, not to be less medicalised or less controlled by medicine, but to increase the degree to which life is medicalized^[13] and to multiply the number of cures that can put an end to one's continuous and natural torments. Individuals have now abandoned any possibility of solving their problems themselves and rely on the expert and medical science and its evolution to solve life's inconveniences.

We have reached a point in human history where further attempts to make the world a better place will include not only changes to the world but also changes to humanity, perhaps with the consequence that we, or our descendants, will cease to be human in the sense in which we understand this concept.^[14] Biomedicalised change represents the shift from medical control over external nature to control and transformation of inner nature, while remaining anchored in the practices of projects for the normalisation, regulation and protection of life ensured by the framework of medicalization.^[15] In order to grasp this, one must first refer to enhancement, understood as the

primary criterion that shifts the paradigm of medicalisation to that of biomedicalisation. By this term, we mean the use of biomedical technology to achieve purposes other than merely curing or preventing disease: in other words, we refer to the possibility of implementing measures aimed at improving what today are natural human provisions, i.e. the conditions that currently characterise man's nature and potential. From this definition, it can be understood that enhancement is a practice that condenses all the techniques that can increase people's psychological well-being, cognitive and physical capacities, or lifespan. Today's biologically-minded citizens must engage in a constant work of self-assessment as well as adjustments to behaviour, diet, lifestyle and pharmaceutical regime in response to the changing needs of a susceptible body within a biomedicalisation mechanism that diverts its gaze from normalisation to optimisation through transformation. In designing, experiencing and comparing the new relationships between truth, power and commerce that affect our lives, our suffering and our bodies in challenging vital limits, biological citizens are redefining what it means to be human. We are far from being able to create situations whose aim is to enhance human beings by going beyond the criteria of normality since its very concept is already clear in the view of those who create the opportunities for enhancement. It is for this reason that the very fact that medicalisation represents a framework of our actions which determines the explanatory possibilities of subjectivity (decided by biopolitical power) means that even enhancements due to genetic engineering are linked to an idea of normality that is deeply rooted in subjectivity. Moreover, with free-market eugenics,^[16] the essence of biopolitical power has been revived, namely the all-encompassing nature of its activities in relation to sovereign power. This is because sovereign power would have acted by defining the characteristics that were to be preserved, whereas today it is no longer the state that prescribes this, but individuals who voluntarily choose to forego certain characteristics over others and do so in order to help their children adapt to a shared normality. One can see how genetic manipulation, rather than an act of total freedom, represents an act of extreme normalization, since the medicalisation that leads to normalisation, able as it is to dictate modes of subjectivation, also determines the possibilities that the subjects themselves choose to lend to their posterity through genetic action. It is under this medicalised and normalising perspective that the biomedical paradigm continues to shift; it does not offer the possibility of providing situations which are completely free of medicalisation since medicalisation itself is the framework in which acts are performed, including enhancement. Human enhancement is thus a radical form of normalisation resulting from the frame of medicalisation that gives meaning to subjectivity and the real. It is likely that a fundamental paradigm shift marking a movement from population control to the fulfilment of an individual's desires will take place in the future, and only such a situation will lead to a new form of humanity that can be termed post-human.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that she has no commercial associations (e.g. consultancies, stock ownership, equity interest, patent/licensing arrangement etc.) that might pose a conflict of interest in connection with the submitted article

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